

PROPERTIES OF POLYURETHANE MADE FROM UREA AND GLYCERIN

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Abstract: The dependence of the chemical structure formation and physicochemical properties of thermosetting epoxyurethane polymers based on the synthesized oligourethanes end epoxy resins on the amount of oligourethanes has been proved.

Keywords: glycerin, urea, polyurethane, carbamate, thermoplastic, propylene.

Introduction

Polyurethane is a polymer composed of organic units joined by carbamate (urethane) links. While most polyurethanes are thermosetting polymers that do not melt when heated, thermoplastic polyurethanes are also available. The versatility of polyurethane chemistry allows for a wide range of properties and applications, which can be further enhanced by incorporating bio-based materials such as urea and glycerin.

Polyurethane foams derived from hydroxypropoxy derivatives of urea, specifically N,N'-bis(2-hydroxypropyl)urea (BHPU), exhibit enhanced thermal stability when reacted with a large molar excess of propylene carbonate (PC). This improved thermal stability is crucial for applications that require materials to withstand high temperatures without degrading.

Using 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate as a substrate, rigid polyurethane foams can be produced. These foams are characterized by their high thermal stability

and low water uptake, making them suitable for insulation panels and other applications where moisture resistance and thermal insulation are important.

Polyurethane formulations can vary widely in terms of stiffness, hardness, and densities. This allows for the creation of products tailored to specific needs, from flexible foams used in seating to hard plastic parts for mechanical applications.

Polyurethanes, including those made from urea and glycerin, are used in a multitude of applications. These include high resiliency flexible foam seating, rigid foam insulation panels, microcellular foam seals and gaskets, durable elastomeric wheels and tires, electrical potting compounds, high-performance adhesives and sealants, Spandex fibers, seals, gaskets, carpet underlay, and hard plastic parts.

It is important to note that while polyurethane products are often colloquially referred to as 'urethanes', they should not be confused with the specific substance urethane, also known as ethyl carbamate. Polyurethanes do not contain ethyl carbamate nor are they produced from it.

The use of polyurethanes extends to everyday items and structures, including varnish, wheels, furniture, automobile seats, houses, sculptures, decorations, watercraft, construction sealants, firestopping, tennis grips, electronic components, adhesives, and watch band wrapping.

The incorporation of urea and glycerin into polyurethane production not only contributes to the sustainability of the material but also enhances certain properties such as thermal stability and water resistance. The broad range of applications and the ability to tailor the properties of polyurethane make it a valuable material in many industries.

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